

Structural Garment Development Using Origami-Inspired Draping Techniques

Harini M S¹, Dr. Geetha Margret Soundri², Devaki s³

MSc Student¹, Department of Costume Design and Fashion, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore- 641014

Associate professor², Department of Costume Design and Fashion, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore- 641014

Research Scholar³, Department of Costume Design and Fashion, PSG College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore

Abstract- — Origami presents numerous forms and intricate production techniques, and it is considered one of the essential contemporary art forms. To enhance the creative expressions in fashion design, this paper outlines the various ways origami art is applied in fashion design by examining its external and structural features, conducting experimental analysis of fabric properties, and summarizing suitable expressive techniques. The findings indicate that origami's folding applications and clothing design can be achieved through techniques such as ironing, crimping, stitching, texture shaping, and repeated combination moulding, including pattern deformation folding, fabric transformation folding, and modular combination folding. The use of folding techniques in creating three-dimensional clothing designs and surface textures is emphasized. To reduce manufacturing flaws and enhance mechanical performance, this work employs curved-crease origami principles to manufacture composite structures using NCFs. The results reveal that the biaxial NCFs are able to develop adequately without any wrinkle flaws over origami-based geometries. Situation-based design thinking motivates designers to be creative by applying their expertise and abilities to develop design solutions. This research explores design thinking and investigates an approach to fashion design education that supports students in cultivating three-dimensional creative abilities. The project involved from the Fashion and Design Department and was conducted as a planned activity. Origami served as the inspiration to explore complex structures, starting with two-dimensional ideas and progressing to three-dimensional shapes, first using paper and later translated into fabric for a skirt design. The general results indicate that the project offers a successful method for fashion design education designed to encourage creative thinking. This teaching approach to fashion design and pattern making offers a contemporary, practical learning experience for design students, allowing them to develop creative designs by combining the production process with the broader design strategy. These encouraging findings suggest that work must go on concerning automation methods based on origami.

Keywords: Pattern innovation, Fabric folding, Draping techniques, Wearable sculpture.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since Cai Lun invented papermaking during the Han Dynasty in China, origami has undergone continuous development and transformation, remaining an essential cultural and artistic expression to this day. Initially, origami was utilized in religious ceremonies; it is evident in Japanese offerings and Chinese Buddhist tributes. As papermaking technology advanced, origami techniques gradually permeated society and found applications in everyday life. In Guizhou, the Dong people, an ethnic minority group, possess a distinctive sewing bag that incorporates origami techniques.

Flexible objects have the capacity to bend, twist, or stretch when subjected to fluid flows. This capacity for shape alteration is frequently a determining factor for the survival of biological organisms in the presence of strong winds or water currents. It significantly diminishes the drag that plants experience in comparison to a rigid structure, enabling them to withstand

breakage and uprooting. In a groundbreaking study, Vogel documented the transformation of leaves into cone shapes, resulting in a slower increase in drag with wind speed, rather than the expected evolution as the square of the flow velocity observed in rigid objects at high Reynolds numbers, where it increases almost linearly. This reduction in drag is attributed to the decrease in the frontal area exposed to the flow, coupled with a streamlining effect. The reconfiguration of plants has since been thoroughly documented, highlighting the widespread nature of this self-protective mechanism. Engineering has also embraced the principle of flexibility, increasingly prioritizing compliant components over rigid alternatives.

These components are more adaptable and resilient to changing environments, and their capacity for shape-shifting enhances their versatility. Notable applications include the use of soft valves that autonomously adjust the flow rate through the deformation of flaps, as well as improved propulsion through

flexible wings and propellers. In all these scenarios, achieving passive control over deformation serves as an effective method for regulating the fluid loading on the structure. To gain a deeper insight into the mechanisms that govern the reconfiguration of flexible systems in flow, experimental studies have been conducted on simple man-made geometries, which are also suitable for theoretical modeling. Groundbreaking two-dimensional experiments were performed on the deformation of a flexible fibre tethered in a soap film flow, as well as on a strip in an air crossflow.

These studies report the bending of the structure as the flow velocity increases and its effect on the scaling of drag with velocity. The coupled fluid-elastic problem is theoretically modeling, quantitatively aligning with experimental findings. Given that the deformation of slender flexible structures is highly dependent on their dimensionality, research has subsequently expanded to three-dimensional configurations. A thin, flexible disk, cut along a radius and anchored at its center, rolls into an increasingly tighter cone in a water flow of rising speed, mirroring the leaf roll-up observed by Vogel.

Conversely, when the experiment is replicated with an uncut disk, it is compelled into a series of conical draping modes. These two examples demonstrate how alterations in the geometry of a sheet affect its deformation in a flow and the resulting changes in drag. Nevertheless, there are limitations on the shapes that such thin-walled structures can assume. A small thickness energetically favors bending during stretching deformations, leading them to primarily undergo length-preserving deformations. Consequently, for example, the maintenance of Gaussian curvature complicates the transformation of an initially flat plate into a double-curved shape. To begin with, this paper outlines key areas to consider for the simplest origami-based design scenarios: when the final product closely resembles the origami model it is derived from. These considerations will aid in the development of related products by offering a conceptual framework for origami-based design, pinpointing essential decisions throughout the process, and fostering a clear thought process.

Such considerations provide a fundamental comprehension of this burgeoning field and may establish a basis for future design methodologies, including those that incorporate more advanced levels of origami-based design abstraction. It can be expanded and repeatedly closed like a sandwich, and it is both compact and portable. It is evident that origami art represents a highly versatile art form that can be utilized in a broad spectrum, demonstrating its distinctive creativity and fascination throughout its extensive history. The utilization of origami across different sectors not only showcases the unique

creativity of its practitioners but also enhances the practical value of products to satisfy individuals' elevated aesthetic desires. When it comes to origami, the material is crucial. Paper, an elastic material that likes to remain flat, is used in artistic origami; nevertheless, other materials are better suited for engineering. In essence, creasing a sheet involves bending it past its yield point, causing plastic deformation. When surfaces have pleat folding, the forces causing the crease patterns to interact will be balanced by physics. This is crucial when using two-dimensional (2D) sheet material to construct three-dimensional (3D) structures. It is possible to produce or self-fold 3D structures with ease if the material is suitably pieced together and creased so that each area on the material wants to locally bend and deform to the desired configuration.

Through its many structural characteristics, origami offers tool kit for transformation. Fashion designers can broaden the current framework for garment production while exploring new forms with the use of origami's diagrammatic linkages. This study examines a novel design method created to assist students in producing structurally innovative structures, drawing influence from origami. Each fold needs to be thoughtfully planned and carried out to make sure the finished piece maintains its desired shape. This feature involves the capability to shape the yarn into foldable structures that ensure a 3D design, allowing the form to progress from basic to more intricate sculptural shapes.

The yarn is woven into loops, enabling the fabric to be created quickly and in various shapes, depending on loop movement, the knitting method, and the type of machine used. By examining prior research on the application of augmented reality technology in pattern design, it becomes clear that there is a lack of studies in this area, highlighting the need to adopt technological advancements, such as augmented reality. Students develop pattern design skills using an origami-style approach due to its various features, such as offering 3D content, aligning virtual and real objects, allowing easy access to virtual objects from any location and at any time, enabling smooth interaction between educators and students, and providing a straightforward and efficient tool.

II. ORIGAMI AND FASHION

The positive approach to using origami as inspiration is increasingly evident in the work of Western designers. An excellent illustration of this strategy is John Galliano's highly regarded Spring Summer 2007 Dior couture show, which was inspired by "Pinkerton's affair with Cio-Cio San, Madame Butterfly." Galliano combined structural origami elements with the iconic Dior form in this collection. "Each look sprouted yet

more miraculous planes of origami folding, their stiff geometries creating necklines like flowers or hovering birds." They developed a line of clothing produced from single pieces of flat material folded in an origami shape with permanently heat-set folds by experimenting with new production techniques. "The brand name alludes to how a piece of cloth ("1D") assumes a three-dimensional shape ("3D") before being folded into a flat surface ("2D"), as well as how wearing it transforms it into a presence that transcends time and dimensions ("5D")."Designers use folding, pleating, tucking, and geometric fabric manipulation to produce structured forms rather of cutting and stitching several parts. It emphasizes: Geometry, Organization, Very little cutting, Silhouettes in sculpture, 3D surface creation.

The way origami-inspired clothing interacts with the human body is a significant aspect. Origami clothing frequently reacts dynamically to movement because folds produce expandable and contractible surfaces. For instance, accordion pleats enable clothing to retract and stretch without the need for elastic fibers. This flexibility preserves sculptural beauty while improving comfort. However, ergonomics must be carefully taken into account by designers to make sure that folded structures don't limit mobility or produce pressure spots.

III. MATERIAL BEHAVIOUR AND FABRIC SELECTION

The qualities of the fabric play a major role in origami draping success. Organza, taffeta, cotton, cotton blends, satin, and other materials with good fold memory and structural stability are frequently favoured. Sharp folds and architectural features are preserved in these textiles. Although they may need more support, softer materials like silk and light cotton produce fluid and organic fold effects. Achieving the intended structural result requires an understanding of fabric thickness, stiffness, elasticity, and drape quality.

IV. STRUCTURAL DRAPING PROCESS

Marking geometric grids on fabric is usually the first step in the origami draping process. Before putting the cloth on a mannequin, the designer pre-folds it in accordance with the intended pattern. Folds are changed after draping to create volume, balance, and proportion. Stitching, topstitching, or heat-setting methods are used to secure the structure. By reducing the number of superfluous seam lines, the garment becomes a coherent sculptural form.

V. AESTHETIC AND FUNCTIONAL IMPACT

Both aesthetic appeal and practicality are improved by origami draping. The surface of the garment gains depth from the rhythm, texture, and shadow effects produced by the repeated folds. Additionally, structurally designed folds can offer expansion and flexibility, allowing clothing to adjust to movement. Origami draping differs from solely decorative textile manipulation techniques in that it combines sculpture and wearability.

Types of Origami Folds Used in Fashion

Pleat Folds:

One of the most popular origami-inspired fashion trends is pleats. They give clothing volume and produce rhythmic patterns.

Square Flower Fold

Dresses, gowns, tops, and ornamental textile panels frequently have the square flower fold. In couture and experimental fashion, where designers experiment with inventive methods to turn fabric into artistic forms, it is particularly well-liked. This method combines geometry, texture, and structural elegance to express the impact of origami on contemporary fashion design.

Cushion Fold

Inspired by the principles of origami, the cushion fold is a fabric manipulation technique that produces raised or puffed square patterns on the fabric's surface. The material appears three-dimensional and cushioned because of the folds that create tiny cushion-like structures.

VI. METHOD OF FOLDING

An origami-inspired three-dimensional structure can be created from a flat piece of fabric by carefully folding it. These folds are made by purposefully manipulating the fabric in accordance with predefined lines or patterns. Marking the fold lines on the fabric is often the first step in the procedure to achieve accuracy and symmetry. After marking, the fabric is folded along these lines to produce geometric shapes like squares, triangles, or pleats, or structured patterns. To keep the structure stable, folds are frequently fastened with sewing, pressing, or heat-setting techniques. To maintain accuracy when folding, designers frequently employ instruments like measuring scales, pins, and ironing processes. Sometimes the required structural appearance is achieved by draping the fabric directly onto a dress form.

Designers may create architectural shapes, textures, and volume with the folding process without having to cut a lot of fabric. This method encourages creative design creation and improves the visual appeal of clothing. Because of this, origami-inspired folding techniques are crucial to contemporary fashion design, especially when it comes to structural draping and fabric manipulation.

↓
 Material / Fabric Selection
 ↓
 Presentation / Production

Design Sketch

Final Garment

VII. DESIGN DEVELOPMENT

Initial concepts are investigated, tested, adjusted, and refined into feasible designs during the design development phase. Sketching, prototyping, fabric selection, fabrication methods, and detailing are all included.

Research & Inspiration
 ↓
 Concept Development
 ↓
 Design Sketching
 ↓
 Design Exploration

VIII. RESULT

The analysis of numerous research and fashion designs demonstrates the importance of origami-inspired methods in contemporary fashion design. Designers are able to produce inventive garment structures and distinctive silhouettes by using origami folds in fabric manipulation. Designers can create intricate three-dimensional shapes out of flat materials by combining origami folding techniques with structural draping techniques. The study also demonstrates how common methods for adding texture, volume, and architectural features to clothing include pleating, tessellation, Miura fold, and geometric folding. These methods preserve flexibility and functionality while improving clothing's visual appeal. By encouraging fabric efficiency and minimizing excessive cutting, designers that experiment with origami principles successfully create innovative and ecological fashion solutions. Overall, the analysis shows that structural draping influenced by origami is a successful design strategy that promotes experimentation, creativity, and innovation in fashion design. The creation of distinctive and eye-catching fashion designs is facilitated by the incorporation of origami principles into clothing fabrication.

REFERENCES

1. Angela BURNS, Arzu VURUŞKAN Izmir University of Economics, Department of Fashion and Textile Design, Izmir, Turkey Online Erişime Açıldığı Tarih (Available online):26 Mart 2019 (26 March 2019).
2. Proceedings of ASME 2014 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences & Computers and Information in Engineering Conference IDETC/CIE 2014 August 17–20, 2014, Buffalo, NY, USA.
3. Sutharsanan Navaratnarajah, James Kratz and Mark Schenk Bristol Composites Institute, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK
4. . Deng Y. An Analysis of origami's creativity in contemporary design art. *Arts Criticism*. 2012; (10): 108-112.
5. Ana-Ramona CIOBANU, Mirela BLAGA Gheorghe Asachi Technical University of Iasi, Faculty of Industrial Design and Business Management, Iasi, Romania
6. 07 September 2015 Citation in Bib Tex format Ubicomp '15: The 2015 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing September 7 - 11, 2015 Osaka, Japan.
7. N. A. A. Elwan1, *, H. S. E. A. Abdelaal1,2 , R. A. M. Elshiekh1 , H. A. A. Alnawawy1 , and E. H. A. Rezk1 1 Department of Clothing and Textile, Faculty of Home Economics, Al-Azhar University, Tanta, Egypt 2 Department of Fashion Design and Arts Department, College of Design and Applied Arts, Taif University, Taif, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
8. Liliia Zhuravel-Zmieieva () Faculty of Design, Kyiv National University of Technology and Design, Kyiv, Ukraine.
9. Xinyi Huang, Sarah Kettley & Sophia Lycouris (2024) Developing Shape Change-Based Fashion Prototyping Strategies: Enhancing Computational Thinking in Fashion Practice and Creativity, *Fashion Practice*, 16:2, 282-310, DOI: 10.1080/17569370.2024.2335615.
10. The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202503948>.